

SPREADING OF LIQUIDS ON MERCURY SURFACE

By BHOLANATH GHOSH

The laws of spreading of water containing traces of HCl, H₂SO₄, HNO₃, H₃PO₄, NaCl, KCl, RbCl, CsCl, and colloidal graphite solution irradiated by X-rays have been studied on Hg surface, and the number of H⁺ or alkali ions necessary to produce a critical area of 1 cm² has been evaluated. The nature of the spreading forces the significance of Harkin's coefficient controlling the spreading phenomenon have also been discussed.

The spreading of liquids and solutions on filter paper has been studied in detail by Prasad and the author in a series of papers (Prasad and Ghosh, *Kolloid Z.*, 1938, 84, 275; 1937, 79, 19; Ghosh, *Bull. Pat. Sc. Coli. Phil. Soc.*, Jan. 1941. cf. Burdon, "Surface Tension and Spreading", p. 28). The mechanism of such spreading as controlled by adsorption has also been discussed therein. The structure of the solid, its field of force and free energy, besides the viscosity, surface tension and angle of contact of the liquid play important rôle in the spreading phenomena. For arriving at a relevant law of spreading the method of the Theory of Dimension was used. The spreading of one liquid A over another B belongs to an entirely different category, and demands a reduction of the free energy for the whole system for spreading to occur. For this the Harkin's coefficient (S_{AB}) must be positive,

$$S_{AB} = \gamma_B - \gamma_A - \gamma_{AB}$$

Here γ_A and γ_B are the surface tensions of the two liquids and γ_{AB} is the interfacial tension between the two liquids. The corresponding energy condition for spreading of liquid A over solid B is

$$2\gamma_A < \gamma_B (1 + \cos\theta)$$

i.e. the adhesion of the liquid for the solid B must exceed the adhesion of the liquid itself. The condition for equilibrium of a liquid over a solid, exposing contact angle θ is

$$\gamma_B = \gamma_{AB} + \gamma_A \cos\theta.$$

Hence the previous equation. $\gamma_A \cos\theta$ is known as the adhesion tension of the liquid. This equation imposes an impossible condition for spreading, even when θ is 0. But experimentally we find that even an equivalence of the two sides of the formulae leads to spreading. Coming to the spreading of liquids on mercury, we find that for spreading to occur, in the case of non-spreading liquids, a minute quantity of an active substance, called promotor, is necessary. The action of the promotor is to change the nature of the surface over which the spreading is occurring by forming a monomolecular layer of some ion over the spreading surface. This reduces the value of γ_{AB} and hence the spreading forces begin to preponderate over forces that try to keep the liquid collected in the form of a drop. In the case of spreading of water on mercury it is found that the addition of a minute quantity of acid or salt (about 10⁻⁶ g. of promotor per g. of water) is an important necessity for spreading. The author finds that salts of the alkali metals behave like acids but not to that degree of spreading efficiency. Traces of metallic hydroxides, however, stop spreading. It is to be mentioned here that irradiation of water, containing traces of colloidal gold or graphite, with X-rays also produces spreading even without addition of acids. Such irradiation effect in the case of spreading of heavy mineral oils is already known from the work of Stenstrom and Vigness (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1939, 43, 531) who find that illumination by ultraviolet light of wave-length less than 2800 Å induces spreading power in oils, perhaps by making a small fraction of the molecules unsaturated.

Irradiation of light and heavy paraffins by γ -rays, X-rays or ultra-violet light also produces similar effect (Allen, Grant and Burdon, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1937, 33, 153). The following are the laws for spreading of irradiated oils and paraffins on water (Stenstrom and Vigness, *loc. cit.*, p. 298; Landt and Volmer, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1926, 122, 398).

In the initial stage of spreading,

$\frac{da}{dt} \propto A$, where A is the area of the drop at instant T , since spreading began. At a later

stage, $A \propto t^4$.

It is well known that the presence of copper, gold and similar ions affects the laws of spreading profoundly (Meyers, and Harkins, *Nature*, 1937, 139, 36; Mitchell, Rideal and Schulman, *ibid.* p. 625; Burdon, *Proc. Phys. Soc.*, 1926, 38, 148).

It should be mentioned here that the quantity of these ions also, must be very minute, i.e. less than 10^{-6} g. per g. of water, otherwise the velocity of spreading will be too great for convenient observation.

The broad features of spreading of liquids on Hg consists of two parts *viz.*, (a) A very rapid spreading in the beginning, which can only be timed by special devices, and where spreading depends on the number of active ions, reaching the interface from the volume of the spreading liquid. Here the velocity of spreading is in general directly proportional to the radius of the liquid film (Burdon, Fuller and Gibson, *loc. cit.*) though wide departures from this law are also met with, in the case of some solutions which aspect will not be treated here. (b) A slower second stage, where the velocity of propagation of the liquid front is generally constant. The area covered by the liquid at the point where transition of laws takes place is found to be proportional to the volume of the drop at constant concentration of the acid. In order to obtain 1 sq. cm. value for this critical area a fixed volume of the liquid is necessary for each concentration of the acid. This volume is, however, inversely proportional to the concentration of the acid if the latter be varied. It can be easily calculated from the observed data obtained by previous workers that 10^{14} molecules of monobasic acids, organic or inorganic, are necessary for obtaining a critical area of 1 sq. cm. (Burdon and Oliphant, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1927, 23, 205). After the second stage, during which slow adsorption of the residual ions from the solution is taking place from areas previously covered as well as migration of ions from areas previously covered is occurring, a third stage sets in, where almost pure liquid is spreading. Here the velocity of spreading is decaying in an exponential manner. The intrinsic importance of the second critical area has not been worked out as yet.

EXPERIMENTAL

Over the horizontal surface of mercury, parallel to it, and a few centimeters apart from it, a glass plate with two arrays of parallel straight lines, mutually perpendicular to one another, was placed. The glass plate had a central hole, through which the liquid could be poured over mercury. Photographs of the spreading liquid film were taken on a cinematograph film, moving at a known speed, with the help of a Cine camera, for studying the laws in the initial portion of spreading. The arrangement for photography and the method of dropping is the same as that adopted by Burdon and Oliphant (*loc. cit.*). For later stages, observations with a stop-watch could be conveniently taken. For the first stage some observations were also taken with stop-watches. In some cases by the application of a proper potential

difference between Hg surface and the drop the latter could be held stationary and by opening the electric circuit the drop was allowed to spread. These types of electrically controlled spreading will be the subject matter of a subsequent paper. In some cases after the drop had spread up to a certain distance, the electric field between the spreading drop and Hg was put on in such a way that the drop began to contract and it came back gradually to its original radius. The lower branches of the curves (Fig. 2) reveal this contraction phenomenon, and the position at which the field is put on is marked with double arrow-heads.

For the direct determinations of the spreading pressure, the torsion balance used by Adams and his co-workers for studying force-area curves of films spread on water has been used by the present author.

For the spreading of weak acid solutions, conductivity water, either pure or contaminated with traces of colloidal metals and irradiated by X-rays, and electrolytic solutions of the alkali chlorides the following laws are valid.

Stage 1, $V_1 = K_1 r$, where K_1 is constant; Stage 2, $V_2 = K_2$, where K_2 is another constant; Stage 3, $V_3 = V_3 e^{-\gamma(r-r_0)}$, where r is the radius of spreading film at a point where V_3 is velocity, λ is a constant and r_0 the value of the radius at which the second stage of spreading comes to an end. Many disturbing factors, however, vitiate spreading according to the third law.

Let v = volume of the drop in c.c., $x N$, the strength of the acid or salt solution in terms of normality N , and r_1 , the radius at which the first break involving transition from law 1 to law 2, then it follows that in area πr_1^2 , $\frac{vx \cdot 6.06 \times 10^{23}}{\pi r_1^2 \cdot 1000}$ ions had been adsorbed. From this we

get the value of p where

$$p = \frac{vx \cdot 6.06 \times 10^{23}}{\pi r_1^2 \cdot 1000}$$

p , denotes the number of equivalent monovalent ions necessary to produce 1 sq. cm. of critical area.

Fig. 1

Curves b-d refer respectively to HCl soln of 0.513 c.c. vol. of conc. $0.2 \times 10^{-3} N$, HCl of 0.302 c.c. vol. of conc. $0.5 \times 10^{-3} N$ and HNO_3 of 0.230 c.c. vol of conc. $1 \times 10^{-3} N$

Fig. 2
(end and subsequent stages)

Curves 1-4 refer respectively to
(1) Distilled water (vol. 0.421 c.c.)
(2) HCl soln. (vide b of fig. 1.
(3) " (vide c of fig. 1.
(4) HNO_3 (vide d of fig. 1.)

Spreading curves for a few typical cases are shown in Figs. 1, 2, 3. Fig. 1 represents the initial stage of spreading up to the first break. Fig. 2 depicts spreading from the onset of the first break up to the limiting range of spreading.

Fig. 4

Spreading of conductivity water (vol. = 0.504 c.c.)

TABLE I

Solution of	Vol. of drop.	Conc. solution.	Radius at which 1st break occurs.	Time at which 1st break occurs.	k_1 .	ρk_1 .
HCl	0.513 c.c.	$0.2 \times 10^{-8} N$	1.402 cm.	0.48 sec.	0.7621	0.391
HCl	0.302	0.5×10^{-8}	1.698	0.50	1.262	0.381
HNO ₃	0.230	1.0×10^{-8}	2.096	0.52	1.842	0.424

TABLE II

N = Normality of acid in g. equivalent per litre.

Solvent and temp.	Promoter.	Conc. of acid or salt soln. $\times 10^4$.	Critical areas in sq. cm.		No. of mol. necessary to produce 1 cm ² of 1st critical area.	$\rho \times 10^{-11}$.	Solvent and temp.	Promoter.	Conc. of acid or salt soln. $\times 10^4$.	Critical areas in sq. cm.		No. of mol. necessary to produce 1 cm ² of 1st critical area.	$\rho \times 10^{-11}$.	
			1st Break	2nd Break						1st Break	2nd Break			
Water at 21°	HCl	N	2.50	15.21	27.52	0.99	Water at 21°	NaCl	2N	2.60	14.18	24.10	2.22	2.23
			4.23	24.88	49.43					4.40	24.00	42.34		
	N/2	N	8.74	26.48	52.74	0.99		N/2	N	0.43	12.57	28.12	2.25	
			6.20	18.60	38.42					8.62	11.49	24.34		
Water at 21°	H ₂ SO ₄	N	5.31	35.80	65.12	0.44	Water at 21°	KCl	2N	4.42	17.68	36.12	3.00	3.01
			3.20	21.55	45.43					5.21	20.71	38.43		
	N/2	N	6.41	22.37	40.18	0.43		N	N	8.21	16.31	29.42	3.02	
			7.23	24.10	44.52					6.42	12.84	24.34		
Water at 21°	H ₃ PO ₄	N	4.42	30.48	53.41	0.29	Water at 21°	RbCl	3N	3.35	18.11	34.21	3.29	3.31
			3.72	24.80	47.52					4.42	23.06	40.43		
	N/2	N	5.20	17.33	30.14	0.30		N	N	6.52	11.85	23.14	3.30	
			6.33	21.42	40.01					5.47	9.86	21.23		
Water at 21°	HNO ₃	N	4.21	23.61	40.41	1.07	Water at 22°	CaCl ₂	4N	4.42	29.63	60.23	3.58	3.62
			3.74	22.44	43.20					5.68	37.86	74.15		
	N/3	N	8.42	15.31	20.14	1.10		N	N	7.42	12.17	27.12	3.66	
			6.72	12.23	20.32					8.12	13.38	29.73		

TABLE III

Spreading liquid.	Time of exposure to X-rays in min.	Vol. of drop in c.c. $\times 20$.	Critical area in sq. cm.		Pseudo-acidic normality $\times 3 \times 10^4$.
			1st break.	2nd break.	
Water containing 10^{-7} g. of colloidal graphite per g. of water and irradiated by X-ray.	2	7.62	20.44	43.52	0.447 N
	4	6.82	18.82	41.42	0.460
	6	6.41	18.27	41.21	0.475
	8	6.22	18.29	40.94	0.490
	10	5.84	17.66	39.12	0.504
	12	5.44	16.84	38.54	0.516
	14	5.00	15.78	37.11	0.526
Temp. = 22°.	16	4.62	14.80	36.44	0.534
	18	4.27	13.83	32.12	0.540

TABLE IV

Temperature etc.	$\gamma_B =$	$\gamma_{AH} =$	$\gamma_A =$	$\gamma_B - \gamma_A - \gamma_{AB}$	Solution.	Harkin's coefficient.	Direct determination of spreading pressure by torsion balance.
30°.	490	420	72		Water	-2	-10
Unit of γ -dynes/cm.	490	425	73		HCl soln.	-7	-15
	490	435	73		HNO ₃	-17	-25
	490	440	72		H ₂ SO ₄	-22	-27
	490	447	72		Water with colloidal graphite	-29	-30

DISCUSSION

Spreading-power Coefficient possessed by Different Types of Ions.—One sq. cm. surface of mercury contains 10^{18} atoms of Hg. For the first critical area to be 1 sq. cm. it is found by calculation that 10^{14} molecules of HCl, 0.44×10^{14} molecules of H₂SO₄, 0.30×10^{14} molecules of H₃PO₄ are necessary, showing that about 10^{14} H⁺ ions are necessary to produce 1 sq. cm. of critical area. But from the divergence in the values of p for the four acids, it is clear that the negative ions also play some part in the spreading phenomenon. For the alkali halides the corresponding values are 2.2×10^{16} , 3.0×10^{16} , 3.3×10^{16} and 3.6×10^{16} molecules for NaCl, KCl, RbCl and CsCl respectively. Thus the field of force of one adsorbed H⁺ ion can affect the field of force of 10 atoms in such a way that non spreading liquids spread easily over Hg. For the alkali halides it can be seen that as the size of the cation becomes bigger, more of such ions must be adsorbed in order to produce the same change in the interfacial tension or interfacial energy.

The Effect of X-ray Irradiation on Water contaminated with Colloidal Impurities.—It has been observed by the author that X-ray irradiation of water containing a small amount of colloidal graphite produces varying amounts of spreading power in the solution depending upon the time of illumination. This means that H⁺ ions with a fair degree of stability have been produced in the liquid, whose number increases with the duration of illumination by X-ray. From the study of the velocity of spreading of these samples of colloidal solutions, it can be inferred that as far as spreading is concerned the charged colloids act in the same way as the ions in acids; and X-rays modify the spreading power. It appears that the structure of the (H₂O)_n aggregates in presence of colloids become less complicated on illumination with X-rays. The effect of such irradiation lasts up to 1 hour, and its effect is primarily to produce some H⁺ ions. With longer period of irradiation the H⁺ ions so produced, are more efficient in changing the interfacial tension between Hg and irradiated solution. This fact, as well as the study of the depolarisation of light scattered by these solutions reveal that the ions produced are clusters of the type H⁺-(H₂O)_n and longer irradiation decreases the value of n , i. e., the clusters grow smaller with longer period of irradiation. The spreading of conductivity water containing traces of fluorescent dyestuff, on Hg surface will be treated in a future paper. In Table III, the pseudo-acidic normality of such water has been calculated by assuming that

10^{14} ions are necessary to produce 1 sq. cm. of critical area and that the pseudo-acid so produced is monovalent.

Spreading Pressure and Adsorption.—The nature of pressure, producing spreading in the initial stage (before the first break) may be of the same type as is present in the adsorption of multimolecular layer of undissociated vapour, or dissociated ion on solid surfaces. Here the field of the spreading force exerted by Hg atoms is very feeble and the spreading pressure is entirely due to higher ionic layers adsorbed temporarily over the first weakly adsorbed layer. But from the first break onward the field of force exerted by Hg atoms comes into operation, of course modified by the field of force of higher adsorbed layers. From the second break onward the spreading is almost entirely controlled by the field of the Hg atoms. Rowley and Innes (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1942, 46, 694) have discussed the nature of these spreading pressures in the case of multi-molecular and multi-ionic adsorbed layers.

Interfacial Tension between Hg and solution and Direct Measurement of Spreading Pressure.—From an inspection of Table IV, it is clear that even with negative Harkin's coefficient spreading is possible. This is also verified by direct torsion balance measurement. This shows that other forces besides those present in Harkin's coefficient must be operative in the spreading phenomena. There may be extra superimposition of Van der Waal, electrostatic, or exchange forces.

Spreading of Conductivity Water on Hg.—The equation according to which conductivity water spreads on Hg surface fits in well with the formula

$$D = 0.0824t^{\frac{3}{2}} \text{ for volume } 0.504 \text{ c.c. or with } v = 0.0309/t^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

where v is the velocity of spreading, D is the diameter of the drop and t , the time of spreading. Similar equation has been developed by Blasius (*Z. Math. Phys.*, 1908, 1, 56) for the motion of a rectangular foil of length l , breadth b , over the surface of water possessing interfacial tension γ between the foil and the film of water, density ρ , and coefficient viscosity η .

$$\gamma = \frac{1.327}{2} \sqrt{\eta \rho l u^3} \quad \text{or} \quad u = \left[\frac{4\gamma^2}{(1.327)^2 \eta \rho l} \right]^{\frac{1}{3}}$$

From dimensional considerations in the case of the spreading of circular film of water of radius r over Hg, l of Blasius's equation has been replaced by r , and the nature of the constant in the equation has been generalised by the present author.